

HAEMOSTATIC AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF THE URACOAN RATTLESNAKE (*Crotalus vegrandis*) VENOM: ISOLATION OF A NEW SNACLECS-LIKE URACOLECTIN WITH COAGULANT ACTIVITY

ACTIVIDADES HEMOSTÁTICAS Y BIOLÓGICAS DEL VENENO DE LA SERPIENTE CASCABEL DE URACOA (*Crotalus vegrandis*): AISLAMIENTO DE UNA NUEVA SNACLECS URACOLECTINA CON ACTIVIDAD COAGULANTE

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ABSTRACT

In this study, a fraction of the venom that possesses coagulant activity was characterized and purified. It corresponds to a new protein snaclecs-like (C-type lectin) uracolectin, obtained by three purification steps (anion exchange chromatography, molecular exclusion, and affinity) and HPLC C-18 reverse phase chromatography as final criterion of purity. Prothrombin time (PT) and activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT) of human plasma were shortened by the addition of uracolectin. Uracolectin exhibited reduction of the coagulant activity on plasma; however, no coagulant effect was observed on fibrinogen, which correlated with the snaclecs mechanism of action on the coagulation cascade. It was heat stable up to about 37°C, losing total activity at 60°C; it was constant at pH 7 and not inhibited by EDTA and/or benzamidine. Uracolectin had no activity in the platelet inhibition assays with ADP. Finally, the purified protein was sequenced giving as N-terminal DLPSGWSSYEGH and DGPSGWSSYEGH matching with C-type lectins with coagulant activity isolated from *Crotalus oreganus helleri*, *C. adamanteus* rattlesnakes and Habu *Protrobothrops flavoviridis*. This study evidenced the presence of a novel C-type lectin-like protein named uracolectin.

KEY WORDS: C-type lectin, haemostasis, PT, PTT, Serpentes, Viperidae.

RESUMEN

En este estudio una fracción de veneno con actividad coagulante fue purificada y caracterizada, correspondiendo a una nueva proteína *snaclecs* (Lectina Tipo C) nombrada uracolectina. Fue obtenida por tres pasos de purificación (cromatografía de intercambio aniónico, exclusión molecular y afinidad) y cromatografía HPLC de fase reversa, como criterio final de pureza. Ambos, el Tiempo de Protrombina (PT) y el Tiempo Parcial de Tromboplastina (aPTT) fueron reducidos por la adición de la uracolectina. Esta demostró producir la reducción de la actividad coagulante en plasma; sin embargo, ningún efecto fue observado sobre el fibrinógeno, lo cual se correlaciona con el mecanismo de acción de las *snaclecs* sobre la cascada de coagulación. Uracolectina fue estable a los 37°C y a un pH 7 y no inhibida por EDTA y/o benzamidina, perdiendo totalmente su actividad a los 60°C. Uracolectina no tuvo actividad en el ensayo de agregación plaquetaria con ADP. Finalmente, la proteína purificada fue secuenciada dando como N-terminal DLPSGWSSYEGH y DGPSGWSSYEGH relacionándose con Lectinas Tipo C con actividad coagulante, aisladas de *Crotalus oreganus helleri*, *C. adamanteus* rattlesnakes y Habu *Protrobothrops flavoviridis*. Este estudio demostró la presencia de una nueva Lectina Tipo C-similar (*snaclecs*) nombrada uracolectina.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Lectina Tipo C, hemostasia, PT, PTT, Serpentes, Viperidae.

INTRODUCTION

The accidents caused by venomous snakes represent global pathologies with the connotation of Collective Health problems, especially associated with the tropical and subtropical regions. The ophidic accident has been classified as a neglected disease, despite its high incidence, severity and the serious and permanent functional sequels that could occur in affected individuals; coupled in some cases with its potential mortality (White 2000, Chippaux 2008, De Sousa *et al.* 2013). More than 90% of the ophidic accidents in America are caused by the Viperidae (Russell *et*

al. 1997). The venoms from this family are a rich source of metalloproteases (SVMP), serine proteases (SVSP) and snaclecs proteins (C-type lectins). C-type lectins exist in the 88% of Viperidae *family* (Tasoulis & Isbister 2017), affecting numerous physiological processes, including the coagulation cascade, the fibrinolytic system, the platelet function and the blood pressure (Markland 1998, Mion *et al.* 2002). Furthermore, snaclecs proteins have facilitated the study of several mechanisms, implicated in blood coagulation and platelet activation. They are proteins forming a basic structure, assembling two subunits α and β , and

establishing heterodimers via a typical domain-changing motif (Arlinghaus & Eble 2012). Snaclecs have also been found in South American *Crotalus* snake venom; a genus extensively represented and distributed into groups, according to their geographical distribution (Tan & Ponnudurai 1990). In this work is described the purification and characterisation of a new snaclecs-like (uracolectin) coagulant toxin. This study may offer helpful insights, into the responsibility of this protein in pathophysiological conditions, including thrombosis and haemostatic alterations in the ophidic envenomations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Reagents

Sodium chloride, sodium citrate, sodium azide, tris, hydrochloric acid, sodium hydroxide, Coomassie blue, acrylamide, bis-acrylamide, ammonium per-sulphate, glacial acetic acid, temed, glycerol, sodium bicarbonate, Folin reagent (Sigma-Aldrich, Missouri, USA). Ion exchange chromatography columns, molecular exclusion and affinity (Mono Q10/10 HR), (GE, Healthcare, USA) Protein pack 125 (Waters, USA), Heparin-Sepharose 6 Fast Flow (GE, Healthcare, USA). Chromogenic substrates and human fibrinogen (10% w/w of plasminogen as contaminant) were obtained from Chromogenix AB (Milano, Italy) and (KabiVitrum, Sweden), respectively. Molecular mass standards for SDS-PAGE were from Bio-Rad Laboratories Ltd (California, USA).

Mice

Experiments were carried out using CD1 mice (18-22 g) purchased from the Animal House of the National Institute of Hygiene "Rafael Rangel", Caracas (Bolivarian Republic of Venezuela). Animals were supplied with water and food *ad libitum*, until use.

Venom

The venom pool was obtained by manual extraction of six snakes of both sexes of *C. vegrandis* species (uracoan rattlesnake), from the region of Urocoa, Sotillo District (Monagas state, Venezuela) (8°59'51.5 "N; 62°19'45.1 "W).

Uracoan rattlesnakes inhabiting the eastern Venezuelan territory, in a dry tropical climate region of ~2,105.00 km² (Köppen 2011), characterised by average temperatures of 28°C, with pluvial annual precipitations from 1220 to 1800 mm; relative humidity from 50 to 75%,

located at 10.00 meters altitude, in a typical vegetation formation of savannah, pastures, palm forests, deciduous forests (summer forest) and chaparrals (Pifano 1961). The snakes were maintained in captivity, in the Serpentarium of the Tropical Medicine Institute, Universidad Central de Venezuela (Caracas, Venezuela). Venom was filtered through a 0.45-µm membrane, lyophilised, divided into 30 mg samples and stored at -20°C, until use.

Protein concentration determination

The crude *C. vegrandis* venom and uracolectin protein concentrations were determined following the method by Lowry *et al.* (1951).

Chromatographic fractionation of *C. vegrandis* venom

The fractionation was accomplished by following three chromatographic steps. First, samples of *C. vegrandis* venom were run in a preparative process using a Mono Q HR 10/10, anion exchange chromatography column (GE Healthcare Life Sciences, Uppsala, Sweden). The venom solution was adjusted to 30 mg load range sample in 1 mL of 25 mM Tris-HCl buffer, pH 8.1, and applied with the same buffer to a equilibrated column. The proteins were eluted with a lineal gradient of 0-1 M NaCl diluted 25 mM Tris-HCl buffer, pH 8.1. The chromatography steps were carried out in an automated chromatographic station Biologic Duo Flow (BIORAD, USA) and monitored at 280 nm.

Second, the eluted fractions with the higher coagulant activity (Fraction IV) from anionic exchange chromatography was applied to a Protein-Pack 125 column (Waters, USA) equilibrated with 50 mM ammonium acetate pH 6.9 plus 125 mM NaCl (equilibrium buffer). The FIV sample (3 mg/100 µL) was dissolved in equilibrium buffer and injected into the column. The elution was carried out with the same solution at 0.1 mL/min flow rate and monitored at 280 nm.

Third, the fractions 8 and 9 (250 µg) with the higher coagulant activity were applied to a Heparin-Sepharose 6 Fast Flow affinity chromatography column (GE Healthcare Life Sciences, Uppsala, Sweden) at 25°C, with a maximum flow capacity of 5 mL and adjusted to 2 mL/min. The fraction displaying the highest coagulant activity was graphed, lyophilized and named as uracolectin.

To evaluate the purity criterion of uracolectin

obtained in the previous steps, separation was completed by a reverse-phase Simmetry® C-18 column. 20 µg/µL of sample was loaded into the HPLC column. The mobile phase includes methanol (Solvent A) and 0.5% acetic acid solution (Solvent B). The column was temperature regulated at 25°C and the injection volume was kept at 20 µL. A gradient elution was carried out by fluctuating the proportion of solvent A to solvent B. Entire analysis time per sample was 105 min. HPLC chromatograms were sensed at three different wavelengths (310, 280 and 272 nm) by a UV detector. The toxin was identified by its retention time and run with standards under the same methodology.

SDS-PAGE analysis

Polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (12%) was done (Laemmli 1970), using a Mini-Protean II system (Bio-Rad Laboratories, Hercules, CA).

Determination of Lethal Dose Fifty (LD₅₀)

The LD₅₀ for crude venom was determined by intraperitoneally (i.p.) venom injection in mice (18-22 g) and calculated according to the Spearman-Kärber method (1978). Five mice per dose (2.40 to 6.85 µg/µL) were used.

Minimum Haemorrhagic Dose (MHD)

Haemorrhagic activity for *C. vegrandis* crude venom or uracolectin was assayed by Omori-Satoh *et al.* (1972) method. The MHD was expressed as the minimum amount of venom (µg dry weight) that injected intradermally into mice, produces a haemorrhagic lesion of 10 mm diameter 4 h later. Aliquots of 0.1 mL PBS containing 10, 14, 16 and 20 µg of venom were injected into the shaved dorsal skin of each of three CDI mice. The animals were sacrificed after 4 h, the dorsal skin was detached, and the diameter of the lesions was measured on the inner surface of the skin in two directions. The MHD was estimated using the regression equations that relate the doses of venom, with the mean diameters of the haemorrhagic lesions. It was expressed as the amount of venom, which causes a haemorrhagic spot of 10 mm. Phosphate buffer saline (PBS) was used as a negative control.

N-terminal sequencing

Uracolectin displaying coagulant activity was transferred from SDS-PAGE 10-20% Tricine-gel on to a PVDF membrane (Immobilon-P, Millipore, USA) using a Semi-Dry Transblot Cell (Bio-Rad, USA), at 25 V for 1 h. The

membrane was stained with Coomassie R-250, for 5 min and destained with 50% (v/v) methanol for 5 min. The membrane was sent to Iowa State University to determine N-terminal amino acid sequencing of the first 12 amino acids on a 494 Procise Protein Sequencer/140 C Analyzer (Applied Biosystems, Inc., USA).

Coagulant activity on plasma and fibrinogen

The coagulant activity of uracolectin was established following the modified method of Austen & Rhymes (1975). Briefly, 0.1 mL of fresh citrate human plasma or 0.3% human fibrinogen solution in coagulation buffer was prepared. Then, a sample of uracolectin (10 µg/100 µL) in 0.1 mL of 0.05 M Tris-HCl buffer, pH 7.4 (coagulation buffer) containing 0.025 M CaCl₂, at 37°C in a borosilicate tube was supplemented. The solution was mixed thoroughly, and its coagulation time was recorded. Duplicated tests were performed, and the mean coagulation time calculated. The control used was 100 µL of thrombin instead of venom. All experiments and appropriate controls were repeated at least four times, obtaining essentially the same results.

Chromogenic substrate testing thrombin-like uracolectin activity

In order to discard a thrombin-like activity, a thrombin-like (S-2238) commercial chromogenic substrate (Chromogenix AB, Milano, Italy) was used. Briefly, a sample of uracolectin (10 µg) was incubated with 20 µL of substrate (S-2238) and 70 µL of Tris 50 mM-130 mM NaCl pH 8.3 buffers. Then, the uracolectin was maintained at 37°C. The readings (405 nm) were carried out at 0, 5, 15 and 30 min.

Determination of the Prothrombin Time (PT) on plasma

The assays were carried out using standard coagulometric methods as provided by the manufacturer and performed on PT reagent (Thromborel®, Siemens, Sweden). The PTs were carried out by incubating in a water bath, 25 µL of human citrated plasma of healthy members from our laboratory, or 25 µL of 0.3% human fibrinogen solution, at 37°C for 1 min. Then, 25 µL uracolectin was added (in a concentration of 10 µg dissolved in 0.9% saline solution), with the following addition of 100 µL PT reagent, previously incubated at 37°C. Then, it was the immediate observation of the coagule formation, over a measured time. The controls were performed with pool of fresh plasma of healthy members of our laboratory.

Determination of Activated Partial Thromboplastin Time (PTTa) on plasma

The activated partial thromboplastin times assay was performed using standard coagulometric method as provided by the manufacturer (Actin®, Siemens, Sweden) and carried out with the PTT reagent, by incubating 50 µL of human citrated plasma from our laboratory healthy members or 50 µL of fibrinogen, with 100 µL of the aPTT reagent (Actin®), in a water bath at 37°C, for 3 min. Then, 50 µL of uracolectin and 100 µL of calcium chloride were added, proceeding to the immediate observation of the coagule formation, over a measured time. The controls were done with a pool of fresh plasma of healthy members of our laboratory.

Effect of temperature on uracolectin

To evaluate the temperature effect on purified uracolectin, the method proposed by Mazzi *et al.* (2004) was employed. The uracolectin was incubated for 30 min at different temperatures: 8, 25, 37, 60 and 90°C. Then, the samples were cooled in an ice bath, and the coagulant activity was evaluated, as described above.

Effect of pH on uracolectin

To evaluate the pH influence on uracolectin, the method proposed by Mazzi *et al.* (2004) was used. The protein was incubated at different pH buffers: 3, 7, 9 and 12 and then, the pHs neutralised. After this period was evaluated if uracolectin retained its coagulating activity.

Effect of serine and metalloproteinases inhibitors

Inhibition of coagulating activity was considered by incubating uracolectin in 50 mM Tris-HCl buffer pH 8.2 containing metalloproteinase inhibitors (10 mM EDTA and 10 mM EGTA-Na) or serine proteinase inhibitor (a trypsin or trypsin-like inhibitor) (10 mM benzamidine, and 10 mM PMSF) for 30 min at 37°C. The coagulant activity was established following the proposed method (Mazzi *et al.* 2004).

Effect of uracolectin on platelet aggregation

Platelet aggregation was determined by turbidimetry using a dual channel Chrono-log model 560 CA aggregometer (USA). To evaluate the influence on platelet aggregation of uracolectin (10 µL/150 nM final concentration), crude venom (10 µg) or Tyrode's buffer

(aggregation control) were complemented to 490 µL of platelet rich plasma (PRP). The platelet amount was adjusted to 3.0×10^5 platelets/mL with platelet-poor plasma (PPP). The mixtures were incubated for 4 min at 37°C in silicone-treated glass cuvettes enclosing a stir bar. Aggregation was carried out by 5 µL of adenosine diphosphate (ADP) (10 µM final concentration) and fluctuations in light transmittance were continually registered for 8 min.

The aggregation reaction triggered by ADP/Tyrode's buffer was used, as a reference of 100% aggregation. The percentage of inhibition generated by crude venom or uracolectin was calculated by comparing the light transmittance of ADP-induced aggregation, in the presence or in the absence of venom or uracolectin. The results were recorded as % inhibition of platelet aggregation.

Ethical approval

This research has been approved by Ethics Committee of the Institute of Anatomy of the Universidad Central de Venezuela (March 01, 2018), under certification number 01-03-18, following the norms obtained from the ARRIVE guidelines and were carried out in accordance with the U.K. Animals (Scientific Procedures) Act, 1986 and associated guidelines, EU Directive 2010/63/EU for animal experiments. Trained staff organised all the experimental methods relating to the use of live animals.

RESULTS

Protein content of *C. vegrandis* venom and fraction

The *C. vegrandis* venom protein concentration was 63 mg/mL and uracolectin 2.4 mg/mL.

Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate polyacrylamide gel electrophoretic (SDS-PAGE) profile

The *C. vegrandis* venom and uracolectin electrophoretic profile was evaluated in SDS-PAGE, under reduced conditions (Fig. 1).

Chromatographic profile

The *C. vegrandis* venom, run in a Mono Q HR 10/10 anion exchange chromatographic profile showed 8 predominant peaks, which were designated as FI to FVIII Fractions. Fraction IV was selected (due to its procoagulant characteristics) and subsequently run in a

Protein-pak 125 molecular exclusion chromatography column, producing 9 predominant fractions.

Finally, fraction 8 was chosen out from the 9 fractions obtained by Protein-Pak 125 molecular exclusion (due to its procoagulant characteristics), for the next fractionation step using a Heparin Sepharose chromatographic column; the resulting fractions (F1 and F2) showed two bands at ~21 and 7 kDa, respectively. Then, the two fractions were collected and tested by procoagulant activity, on plasma and fibrinogen. Coagulant activity was displayed in fraction 1 (~21 kDa), which appeared to be a highly purified, by reverse phase C18 chromatography and SDS-PAGE stained with silver staining, now named as uracolectin (Fig. 2).

Lethality and Lethal dose 50 (LD₅₀)

The intraperitoneally crude venom LD₅₀ obtained was 4.36 mg/kg. When testing doses as low as 2.0 mg/kg and 8.0 mg/kg, it was not possible to determine the uracolectin LD₅₀ (Table 1) because the assay requires processing a large amount of crude venom, to obtain enough amount of isolated toxin for the LD₅₀ experiment in the model mouse used.

Minimum Haemorrhagic Dose (MHD) of *C. vegrandis* crude venom and uracolectin

Table 1 shows the average of the area of haemorrhagic activity of crude venom obtained (15.49 µg/mouse), according with the (µg/µL) injected. A mouse injected with 0.9% saline solution was used as control. Uracolectin did not have haemorrhagic activity.

Determination of the prothrombin time (PT) and activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT) of *C. vegrandis* crude venom and uracolectin on plasma

The determination of prothrombin time (PT), and activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT) on plasma (Maduwage & Isbister 2014) using *C. vegrandis* crude venom (10 µg) presented a formed coagulum, at 17.6 s for PT and at 31.5 s for aPTT. Uracolectin (100 µg/mL) showed a coagule at 9.4 s in PT (Control: 12.4) and 5.4 s for aPTT (Control: 30.2) (Table 1).

Procoagulant activity

The procoagulant activity determined in the *C. vegrandis* crude venom and uracolectin are shown in Table 1. Crude venom showed

procoagulant activity by using both amidolytic and coagulant methods. When using amidolytic methods, specifically with S-2238 substrate, it was observed that only crude venom had activity, while uracolectin did not react to it. Additionally, crude venom by coagulant method was the most active ($p < 0.05$). Furthermore, crude venom was significantly more active with plasma as substrate than with fibrinogen ($p < 0.01$).

Heat stability of coagulation activity

The temperature effect on uracolectin (1.1 µg/mL) is shown in Table 1. The temperatures that produced the smallest action over the coagulation time were 25°C and 37°C with a percentage of 6.04 and 11.63% for the plasma. In the case of fibrinogen, the temperature that showed the lowest percentage of action over the coagulation time was 37°C, with a percentage of 2.15%. The optimum temperature of the purified fraction was between 25 and 37°C. The coagulant activity was completely lost at 60°C.

Coagulation activity and pH

The effect of pH on uracolectin (1.1 µg/mL) evaluating the coagulation time is shown in Table 1.

Coagulant activity of uracolectin with inhibitors of serine and metalloproteases

Coagulant activity of uracolectin was evaluated in the presence of protease inhibitors. Metalloprotease and serine proteinase inhibitors inactivated crude venom; while, the uracolectin coagulant activity was not altered by both inhibitors (Table 2).

Chromogenic substrate

The results obtained from the thrombin-like activity tested by the S-2238 substrate showed a positive control of thrombin, yielding a 1800 mUA/mL/mg value. In the case of *C. vegrandis* crude venom, a 796 mUA/mL/mg value was obtained, which indicates that it possesses an activity similar to thrombin. Uracolectin did not present thrombin-like activity.

Amino acid alignment

Amino acid sequences of coagulant protein obtained from NCBI (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>) and UniProt (<http://www.uniprot.org>) databases were performed, to infer sequence relationships. Uracolectin was subjected to N-terminal sequencing by Edman degradation. The first 12

amino acid residues from N-terminal sequencing were determined to be DLPSGWSSYEGH or DGPSGWSSYEGH. The primary sequence of uracolectin showed a maximum identity of 100% with a factor IX/X binding protein A subunit C-type lectin (*Protobothrops flavoviridis*) (Aird *et al.* 2013); C-type lectin 1 and C-type lectin 3 (*Crotalus oreganus helleri*) (Sanchez 2011-Blast: [direct submission]); C-type lectin 1 (*Crotalus adamanteus*) (Rokyta *et al.* 2011); Aa-X-Bp-I (*Agkistrodon acutus*) (Zhu *et al.* 1997); Rhodocytin (*Calloselasma rhodostoma*) (Watson *et al.* 2008) (Fig. 3). The sequence was introduced in the UniProt database (<http://www.uniprot.org/help/submissions>) with SPIN ID COHL88 for uracolectin in *Crotalus vegrandis* assigned accession number.

Effect of uracolectin on platelet aggregation

Crotalus vegrandis crude venom inhibited ADP stimulated platelet aggregation (Sánchez & Rodríguez-Acosta 2016). In contrast, uracolectin at 10 µg per assay did not inhibit ADP-induced platelet aggregation (Table 1).

Figure 1. Electrophoretic profile (12%-SDS-PAGE) of *Crotalus vegrandis* crude venom and uracolectin, under reduced conditions. Lane 1: mass markers; Lane 2: Uracolectin ~21 kDa (silver stain). Lane 3: *C. vegrandis* crude venom (silver stain); Lane 4: *C. vegrandis* crude venom (Coomassie blue stain).

Figure 2. High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) C18-reverse chromatography. Fraction 1 (arrow) displaying coagulant activity was run on a C18 reverse phase column. Elution was performed using a RP-HPLC system at a flow rate of 0.5 mL/minute by a segmented concentration gradient of 0-100% % solvent B in one column volume.

Figure 3. Amino acid comparison of uracolectin with other snake venom proteins. Conserved amino acids as compared to uracolectin are shaded in light gray. C-type lectin factor IX/X was isolated from *Protobothrops flavoviridis*. C-type lectin 1 and 3 were isolated from *Crotalus oreganus helleri*. C-type lectin 1 was isolated from *Crotalus adamanteus*. Aa-X-Bp-I was isolated from *Agkistrodon acutus*. Chain B, Structure of Rhodocytin was isolated from *Calloselasma rhodostoma*. The sequence of uracolectin was deposited in the UniProt database (<http://www.uniprot.org>) with a SPIN ID number 244058.

Table 1. *Crotalus vegrandis* crude venom and uracolectin biochemical, biologic and haemostatic effects.

Part A

(LD ₅₀) (mg/kg)		HA (MHD/μg/mouse)		CA-P/F (sec) ^b Control 18-20 s			
crude	uracolectin	crude	uracolectin	P	F	P	F
				crude (10 μg/mL)		uracolectin (0.613 μg/mL)	
4.36	UD	15.5	0	6.0 ± 0.9	2.5 ± 0.6	4.5 ± 0.7	U

Part B

AM (mUA/mL/mg) ^a		PT (sec) Plasma		aPTT (sec) Plasma		T ^o C (inhibited)	pH optimal activity
S-2238 (thrombin)		Control 12.4 s		Control 30.2 s			
crude	uracolectin	Crude (10 μg/mL)	Uracolectin (100 μg/mL)	Crude (10 μg/mL)	Uracolectin (100 μg/mL)	uracolectin	uracolectin
796	0	17.6 ± 0.9	9.4 ± 1.3	31.5 ± 0.7	5.4 ± 0.6	60	7

LD₅₀: lethal dose fifty.

HA: haemorrhagic activity.

CA-P/F: coagulant activity on plasma and fibrinogen. Coagulant activity was determined by the Austen & Rhymes (1975).

The results expressed in thrombin-like units (IU Thrombin/mg)^b by plotting the clotting times against a calibration curve prepared with a thrombin standard (National Institute for Biological Standards and Control, London, England).

AM: Amidolytic method.^a Amidolytic activity was expressed as DA 405 nm/min/mg protein.

PT: determination of prothrombin time on plasma.

PTT: determination of activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT) on plasma.

T^oC: effect of temperature on uracolectin.

pH: effect of pH on uracolectin.

UD: undetermined.

U: uncoagulable

Sec: seconds.

DISCUSSION

The venom of *C. vegrandis* is composed by a pronounced combination of diverse and numerous enzymatic and non-enzymatic toxins, i.e serine proteases, metalloproteases, acid and basic phospholipases, snake venom proteins, gyroxin, and crotoxin, among others (Viala *et al.* 2015); all with biochemical functions and characteristics that give this venom its lethality (LD₅₀ was 4.36

mg/kg), a fact that has been clearly observed in this investigation.

C-type lectins present in snake venoms are now recognised, as snake venom C-type lectins in a nomenclature suggested by the Exogenous Factor Committee from the International Thrombosis and Haemostasis Society (Clemetson *et al.* 2009). Snake venoms do not present the carbohydrate-binding loop that is

observed in classical C-type lectins, and therefore do not join sugar molecules (Drickamer 1999, Morita 2005). Some hetero-tetramers have been described, but they are regularly heterodimers of alpha (14-15 kDa) and beta (13-14 kDa) subunits, almost exclusively associated covalently via a disulphide bridges. They have been classified in subcategories according to their different haemostatic activities, as follows: *a*) coagulant proteins forming a metalloprotease-lectin combination that links to prothrombin or coagulation factor X; *b*) proteins with anticoagulant properties that properly link to coagulation factors IX, X or thrombin/prothrombin fractions; *c*) platelet aggregation antagonists, affecting platelet aggregation by linking to GPIb in compound with vWF, and integrin $\alpha 2/\beta 1$; *d*) likewise, defined as platelet aggregation agonists, affecting platelet aggregation by linking to GPIb, directly or forming a protein complex with either von Willebrand factor (vWF), or platelet glycoprotein VI, or integrin $\alpha 2/\beta 1$, and/or lectin CLEC1B.

In biological conditions several snaclecs can form non-covalent greater order multimers, which are far more operative in assembling receptors and triggering platelets than covalent multimers (Drickamer 1999). There is an important group of snaclecs acting as thrombin inhibitors, for instance, the Bothrojaracin (BJC) initially purified from the venom of *Bothrops jararaca* and from which various isoforms have been isolated from *Bothrops atrox*, *Bothrops cotiara*, *Bothrops jararacusu*, *Bothrops moojeni* and *Bothrops neuwiedi*, as well as the *Trimeresurus mucrosquamatus* venom (Lu *et al.* 2004). Alternatively, the botrocetin from *Bothrops jararaca* venom and bitiscetin from *Bitis arietans* venom are snaclecs that can form trimolecular complexes with the VWF and the GPIb platelet receptor leading to platelets activation (Drickamer 1999).

On the other hand, some snaclecs such as flavocetin do not seem to have a clear activity in the platelet function, as it has been observed in ADP aggregation inhibition assays with uracolectin in the current work. In assays carried out (Taniuchi *et al.* 1995), the flavocetin does not seem to activate the platelets activation by $\alpha IIb\beta 3$ receptor. Flavocetin inhibits the activation of platelets through the classic pathways of GPIb, throughout the von Willebrand factor, presumably by blocking the binding sites. Nonetheless, flavocetin (10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) had no effect on ADP- and collagen-induced platelet aggregation in PRP (Taniuchi *et al.* 1995). It is unknown if uracolectin could have activity in the presence of collagen, thrombin,

adrenaline or other agonists, which were not tested because there was not a sufficient amount of protein to perform many trials during the characterization of the different activities in this work. If this is the case with uracolectin, it is an open issue that will be sufficiently explored in the future.

The evidence found in this study suggests that uracolectin is a snaclecs protein constituted by a ~21 kDa molecular mass subunit. Uracolectin seems to be present in a *C. vegrandis* proteomic study carried out (Viala *et al.* 2015) through its similarity in molecular mass with some snaclecs spots around 15 to 20 kDas. On the other hand, there are other snaclecs, such the coagulation factor IX-binding protein subunit (SLA-PROFL) (*Protobothrops flavoviridis*), convulxin subunit beta (SLB-CRODU) (*Crotalus durissus terrificus*), crotoctin-1 (SL1-CRODU) (*Crotalus durissus terrificus*) and crotoctin (SL-CRODU) (*Crotalus durissus terrificus*) with similar molecular mass, but with a different N-terminal amino-acid sequence as we will see below. Uracolectin N-terminal amino-acid sequence revealed a relatively high degree of sequence identity with other identified components of the snaclecs lineage. Closely, the identity was higher with snaclecs such as C-type lectin factor IX/X (*Protobothrops flavoviridis*), C-type lectin 1 and 3 (*Crotalus oreganus helleri*), C-type lectin 1 (*Crotalus adamanteus*) and Aa-X-Bp-I (*Agkistrodon acutus*) that with other described homodimeric snaclecs from *C. vegrandis*. The aim to know the complete amino-acid sequence of uracolectin would be an advancement to resolve its homodimeric structure (a protein constituted of two polypeptide chains that are equal in the order, number, and kind of their amino acid residues). The presence of two very similar sequences, which only vary in one amino acid, would seem to express that it is a homodimeric protein. Once the complete sequence of the protein is identified, it will be known with certainty, if it is a dimer. The snaclecs subunits are found to be linked with P-III SVMPs (Clemetson *et al.* 2009). They are covalently connected through P-III SVMPs by an inter-chain disulphide bond. As with other snaclecs, these subunits are heterodimeric proteins with two chains associated by an inter chain disulphide bond (Franssen *et al.* 1983, Hofmann & Bon 1987, Yamada & Morita 1997). The concave dimeric interface forms the ligand-binding site of FX and prothrombin (Kini & Koh 2016, Takeya *et al.* 1992). C-type lectin-like proteins are derived from proteolysis of metalloproteinase/disintegrin precursor proteins; they are non-enzymatic inhibitors of platelet aggregation and haemorrhagic agents, resulting

from common precursors. Thus, these non-enzymatic subunits impart distinct properties, acting together with proteolytic enzymes; consequently, they play a critical role in substrate recognition and selectivity, which allows the accompanying protease to exercise its proteolytic activity (Kini 1996).

Viperidae venom activated consumption coagulopathy is probably the most important systemic syndrome that follows as a result of snake envenoming with procoagulant toxins, but it has also been described in Elapidae and Colubridae snake's envenomations (Markland 1998). This syndrome is caused by the activation of the coagulation via by procoagulant toxins, which are able of causing depletion of coagulating factors, putting envenomed patients at chance of most important haemorrhages (Markland 1998). Uracolectin demonstrated to be a C-type lectin, with potent *in vitro* coagulant effect, which was 4.5 µg/mL. The coagulation cascade is a sequence of reactions, classically separated into three pathways: the contact (also identified as the intrinsic) pathway, the tissue factor (also identified as the extrinsic pathway), and the common pathway (Monroe & Hoffman 2006). Measuring the different stages of coagulation in isolation is a difficult task, especially in stage II, since in this stage the prothrombin is converted to thrombin with the help of thromboplastin (extrinsic or intrinsic) and calcium, showing the endpoint of this reaction by the passage of fibrinogen to fibrin, which is stage III of coagulation.

The preliminary biochemical and haemostatic activity of *C. vegrandis* crude venom on the PT and aPTT, a shortening PT of 38.71% in plasma was observed with respect of the control. For the aPTT there was a 5.70% time increase for plasma, compared with the control; once these data were compared with those early reported experiments (Rodríguez-Acosta *et al.* 1998), in that work a difference between the results was seen on PT and aPTT since the plasma was uncoagulable at 5 min. This could happen because the authors worked with a lower concentration of *C. vegrandis* venom, which reassures that this venom is dose-dependent.

Following the order of experimental findings in the current work, it was decided to measure the (PT), which estimates the extrinsic pathway of coagulation, in the absence and presence of uracolectin. The PT was reduced by 28% in the presence of uracolectin. In the other hand, aPTT quantify the activity of the intrinsic and common pathways of coagulation, which measures the levels of factor I (fibrinogen), factor II

(prothrombin), and factors V, and X. The aPTT was reduced by 82.12% with the addition of uracolectin, which generally measures the levels of factor VIII, IX, XI y XII (Eisenberg *et al.* 1982). The results suggest that the action of this fraction as a procoagulant is carried out on the common pathway of the coagulation cascade, since both the PT and the aPTT times were altered (Rodríguez-Acosta *et al.* 1998, Monroe & Hoffman 2006).

Later, it was explored if due to its protean nature, uracolectin may be thermolabile, and as the temperature increases, a greater amount of the protein could be denatured. The temperature at which the maximum activity of a protein is extended is called "optimal temperature", which is characteristic of each protein. Uracolectin lost its coagulant activity at 60°C, but maintained this activity at 25 and 37°C, demonstrating that it is a relatively heat-resistant protein.

Uracolectin is located at the medium size toxins with a molecular mass of ~21 kDa and it has an optimal neutral pH of 7 for coagulant activity. The pHs 3, 8.2 and 10.6 gave an extension of the coagulation time larger than 100% on plasma and fibrinogen. At pH 7 an extension of 11.63%, in the case of plasma, and 2.15% for fibrinogen was produced, demonstrating the important effect carried out by the pH.

In the experiments using chromogenic substrates, changes in colour could be spectrophotometrically monitored and are proportional to the proteolytic activity. The S-2238 is a chromogenic substrate to evaluate the thrombin-like activity, and has also been used for the determination of prothrombin, antithrombin, platelet factor 3, and heparin in plasma. *Crotalus vegrandis* crude venom proved to have thrombin-like activity, but uracolectin did not. The proteomic study of *C. vegrandis* (Viala *et al.* 2015) showed that the venom had fractions located in the serine proteases migration areas (Mackessy 2009) that presumably displayed this activity.

CONCLUSIONS

The meaning of biochemical and functional characterisation of molecules with toxic activities, which have been isolated from snake venoms, lies not only in the deep damage caused in the envenomed victims, but also to the opportunity of describing new molecules that could be effective tools for haemostatic disorders treatment, or even to enrich the field of research in various areas, such as ultrastructure,

neuropathology, general pathology, etc. In recent years, multiple clinical, biochemical and pharmacological studies have been carried out, which have demonstrated the existence of a universe of enzymatic and non-enzymatic compounds, with pathophysiological activities, in many Viperidae family snake venoms, and also from other snake's families. As this result, several attempts have been made to use many of these purified and characterised molecules, as tools in the therapeutic and research field, which represents an important advance in the use of snake venoms in medicine.

Here, we have standardised a purification methodology, for the isolation of a snake venom (uracolectin) molecule from *C. vegrandis* venom, which had effects on coagulation, and also showed that generated alterations in the coagulation cascade producing changes in the PT and aPTT assays. These glycoproteins will be used in future studies to evaluate their effects on many components of the haemostatic system.

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